

Importance of Mobile Security

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ABSTRACT

Being in the 21st century, technology changes within a particular period of time. As we know the data is obtaining larger day by day so its protection is also coming under the concern. data is growing at a faster rate so securing of data is also an important concern. Technology has covered the way for electronic devices such as smartwatches and smartphones and computers which make our lives convenient, easier and simpler. On the click of a button, we can get small to big information and we can make us updated about every new thing that comes in the market. Nowadays technology becomes that much advance that a person can reach to any point and perform any sort of work within a few seconds like weather it comes to pay bills, online shopping, money transfer, food delivery or to communicate with anyone through messaging apps or social media platforms with ur smartphones. So the data that we exchange daily, for shopping your cards and bank details or address details and contact number or your pictures and videos always need to be secured in the first place. A secured place is always successful in inviting more individuals. And today, securing your data or any kind of information has become an important thing to do. Security itself includes the securing of a person's any kind of data regarding him or her from the unauthorized access, modifications, disclosures or destructions.

KEYWORDS: Mobile security, fake app, data security, mobile attacks

WHAT IS MOBILE SECURITY?

There are many risks associated with mobile landscapes. As the mobile phones are used by everyone at the highest rate so as increasing in cybercrimes such as stealing personal information or data or unauthorized access in one's system and make the information destructive or for making money through ransomware because most of our data is stored on these devices. The practice of keep essentials or data safe from unauthorized access in your mobile phones is what we call MOBILE SECURITY. Whether it is digital or non-digital information, mobile security contains the strategies for managing the processes and tools to detect and prevent the threats to the user who uses mobile phones without knowing the risk of having the personal details on their phones.

FIGURE: MOBILE SECURITY

HOW CAN YOU SPOT FAKE MOBILE APP?

As we are using more and more applications for our convenience by downloading them in our mobile phones and

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using them such as pdf convertor for covert any file into pdf format or for having fun there are many gaming apps which are addicted us to it. But how a person comes to know is that the application is fake or not, or after downloading that app his or her information may get compromised or may not. There are some steps through which you can easily identify that a particular app is fake or not given below.

- Do some research on the following app and if the developer could have few reviews or very little downloads, they could just be starting.
- You must go through the reviews given by the users.
- Check their ratings and make sure you download that app from google play store.
- The app must be verified by google play protection.
- Make sure you must go through the functioning of app what does that app does and also check the images, its font, spelling, and graphics

HOW TO KEEP DATA SECURED IN MOBILE PHONES?

It is important to be conscious when it comes to the privacy of data stored on your mobile phones. With the increasing using of mobile phones the data is stored in phones must be protected by everyone. So that it is safe from unauthorized access. , but it is also critical for individuals to let their personal information be secured. And certain policies are thus planned for the same. Several steps are there which can be taken by one to protect their data in individuals' mobile

phones, most of which are easy to implement and helps to save your data.

- Everyone must turn off their Bluetooth when not in use.
- Set your password not with the four-digit number but with the combination of more than 8 digit password having special characters in it.
- Always try to take back up of your data.
- Don't root your mobile phone.
- Never save your passwords in mobile phones or important information and always try to keep password change within a month and make sure your every social media account has contained different passwords.
- Always update your operating system within a specific period of time.
- You must download an anti-malware system in your mobile phones that protect your mobile from any unauthorized access and keeping your data safe from getting steal as it gives you alert about the virus and blocked the websites which contain virus.
- Never use public wifi, use only and only if there is an urgent need to use it. And if you are using the public wifi make sure you never operate any social media account used only for searching.
- Check app permissions individually to be aware of what data apps are accessing on your phone.
- Don't click on links that are from unknown senders in SMS messages or emails

MOBILE ATTACKS

- There are many ways to sneak into your phone. So protecting your data on individuals phones is a must.
- Mobile malware is the most common attack in and is going inside your phone by fake apps and compromise your phone by stealing your data from the phone and hold to ransom.
- Most common attack seen nowadays is phishing scam in which user being compromised by clicking on SMS which is delivered by fake account on the name of the bank or any financial institution so don't ever click on any link which come in message from an unknown source.
- Another way cybercriminals can sneak malware onto your phone is because of outdated software that may have security vulnerabilities. So be sure to update your mobile operating systems as soon as there is an update

available, so these security vulnerabilities are gone and make your information safe.

ADVANTAGES OF MOBILE SECURITY

Knowledge about being secure your data on the mobile phone is advantageous. It helps everyone to save their data and important information from getting steal and being compromised for ransom. As everyone is using mobile phone for online shopping and for money transfer is it safe to give details on shopping websites if not it can be lead to steal your money from bank and giving personal information is also comes under an important concern so to protect your important and private data you must have knowledge about how to secure your information in mobile phones and what kind of attacks can be done on your mobile phones and their protection to not to get compromised and check the vulnerabilities in your phones and patched them as soon as possible.

CONCLUSION

Mobile security is plays an important role to protect information from unauthorized access and any kind of modification or deletion of information or from being compromised. It should not be taken lightly when considering the result of being compromised. Challenges to maintain the privacy of information are taken into consideration. In this article, security issues of information, fake apps and certain attacks which can steal your information and data from your phones are discussed and how to keep our data secure. Through it is important to maintain the information from an unauthorized access to maintain privacy by having antivirus in your mobile phones.

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